

RECYCLABILITY OF RANDOMLY-ORIENTED STRAND THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Recycling, Compression moulding, Discontinuous reinforcement, Thermoplastic composites

ABSTRACT

Randomly-Oriented Strand composites are a bulk moulding compound type of material comprised of strands of pre-impregnated tape. ROS with high fibre volume fractions (>50%) have attractive mechanical properties, as well as very high formability compared to continuous fibre composites. This material is ideal for compression moulding of small complex parts such as brackets and hinges, where varying wall thickness, tight radii and rib features are common. The use of ROS is therefore a good candidate to replace complex metallic parts that are commonly attached to carbon fibre-reinforced polymers primary structures in modern aircrafts. The aim of this paper was to investigate various recycling approaches for carbon/PEEK ROS composites. Focus was placed on understanding the effect of the initial material state on the consolidation quality and mechanical performance of ROS composites. Two material states were tested, namely the virgin bulk moulding compound and recycled ROS composites obtained from pre-consolidated ROS parts. The recycled charges were placed in the centre of the mould cavity resulting in squeeze flow. Geometry and thickness of the recycled charges was varied. Mechanical performance of flat panels was quantified using a four-point bending test. A significant drop in flexural strength was observed for content of recycled material greater than 30%. Recycled panels made from flat pieces cut from moulded parts had 25% higher flexural strength compared to the baseline panel made of virgin strands.

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to achieve lower weight structures, newly developed aircrafts tend to incorporate more composite materials. The most common way to manufacture aerospace composite parts is to use pre-impregnated continuous fibres with thermoset resin and cure them under applied heat and pressure in an autoclave. This technique suits well the manufacturing of large structural parts with simple geometries. Nevertheless, autoclave processing of pre-impregnated continuous fibre with thermoset resin has several drawbacks: the long manufacturing cycle, the high cost and the difficulty of processing complex shaped parts. Although some complex-shaped parts have successfully been processed with continuous fibre (CF) [1], it still remains labour intensive, time-consuming and costly. For these reasons, hundreds of load introduction components, such as brackets, hinges and fittings are still made of metals. Beyond the obvious drawback of additional weight, aluminium load introduction elements have to be carefully mounted with protections against galvanic corrosion of the carbon fibre reinforced polymer [2]. Thus, there is an interest in the aerospace industry in replacing these complex metallic parts with composites manufactured with a cost effective process.

Short-fibre reinforced composites, which are widely used by the automotive industry, meet the requirement of cost-effective processing. Complex net-shaped parts can be manufactured in short cycle times with processes such as injection moulding or compression moulding thanks to the high-flow moulding that characterizes these low fibre volume fraction composites (30-50%) [3]. Nevertheless, the mechanical properties achieved for these components cannot compare to the performance exhibited by continuous fibre composites and are often not satisfactory for the stringent requirements of the aerospace industry [4].

Recently, a new type of material system that could combine both the advantages of CF and short-fibre composites has emerged in the literature: randomly-oriented strands (ROS) of unidirectional pre-impregnated tape [5], also named discontinuous fibre composite materials [2], [6] or chopped tapes composite materials [7–8]. The advantages of this material system are the high fibre volume fraction (>50%) that gives its attractive mechanical properties and good formability when processed by compression moulding [9–12]. ROS composites are intended to be used for compression moulded net-shaped components having intricate features such as tight radii, reinforcing ribs and mould-in holes.

Randomly-oriented strand materials are rectangular chips cut from a pre-impregnated unidirectional tape (Fig. 1). This material was first introduced by Feraboli *et al.* [4, 6, 13–14, 16], who studied parts made from carbon fibre/epoxy chopped strands. Their work looked into the strand random distribution in flat panels moulded in compression. Other work on carbon/epoxy ROS material was conducted by Tuttle *et al.* [15]. They used the commercially available HexMC AS4/8552 and conducted work on strand orientation and fibre volume fraction as well as tensile properties of flat panels processed under high flow. Following the studies on processing and mechanical properties of flat panels, publications have shown the excellent formability of compression moulded ROS complex parts both with thermoset and thermoplastic resins. Feraboli *et al.* [16] moulded a suspension control arm with carbon/vinylester ROS for the Lamborghini *Sesto Elemento*, a composite technology demonstrator car. The use of ROS composites allowed reducing the weight of the element by 27% compared to the forged aluminium counterpart. Han *et al.* [17] moulded an L-curved beams from carbon/polyethylenimine (PEI). Van Wijngaarden *et al.* [8] were the first to process a deep flange with the carbon/PEEK material system. They were followed by Eguémann *et al.* [18] who moulded a rotorcraft door hinge featuring net-shaped holes also made from carbon/PEEK chopped strands. Most recently, TenCate released several images of complex parts made of thermoplastic and thermoset chopped strands, such as the very complex F-35 helmet optical support structure, which include many features and net-shaped holes [7]. If some of the key properties of ROS composites and their formability were demonstrated, a complete material characterization in terms of processability and performance, as well as a study of processing conditions for the manufacturing of complex parts was missing.

Figure 1: Randomly-oriented strand material from the initial pre-impregnated tape to the finished part.

Picher-Martel *et al.* [11, 19], studied the macroscopic squeeze flow by X-Ray tomography and modelled the squeeze flow in two-dimensions. Selezneva *et al.* [5, 10] studied the influence of strand length on the tensile properties of flat panels and compared the results to the values obtained with a CF quasi-isotropic flat panels processed with the same material system. Landry *et al.* [20, 21] studied the influence of processing pressures on the moulding defects formed during cooling and their repercussion on mechanical properties. LeBlanc *et al.* [22] investigated the effect of processing pressures and strand size on the quality of T-shape part. The critical pressure needed to fill the rib cavity was found to increase with increasing strand size. It was found that the performance of the parts processed at the critical pressure were similar to the ones processed at high pressure.

To the knowledge of the author, a single contribution was made to the field of recycling ROS composites. Eguémann *et al.* [9, 17] proposed a novel technique in the field of recycling thermoplastic: electrodynamic fragmentation. A virgin rotorcraft door hinge was fragmented into small strand-like pieces with this technique. The obtained fragments were then used to reprocess the same rotorcraft door hinges from 100% recycled material. The recycled part was found to yield similar behaviour in the elastic region as the part made from virgin strands. Nevertheless, the recycled part was found to be brittle and lacked the pseudo-plastic region, which could be observed with the virgin part.

In light of the above, the objective of this paper is to investigate various recycling approaches for carbon/PEEK ROS composites. Focus is placed on understanding the effect of the initial material state on the consolidation quality and mechanical performance of ROS composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

In order to evaluate the effect of recycling ROS composites panels were manufactured from material recycled from pre-moulded parts.

2.1 Part manufacturing

The material used in this work was a carbon fibre/polyether ether ketone bulk moulding compound, which consisted of strands cut from a unidirectional pre-impregnated carbon/PEEK tape. The fibre content of this material system was 59% and the strand size was 12.7 mm × 3.2 mm. T-shape parts were manufactured using an instrumented fixture that was mounted on a MTS (Eden Prairie, MN) 250 kN load frame (Fig. 2). The instrumented fixture was made of two H-13 steel platens, both with a square size of 100 mm × 100 mm. Each platen was heated by four 500 W FIREROD® cartridges, which were controlled by two auto-tuning PID controllers from Watlow (St. Louis, MO), one controller per platen. Each platen also consisted of three cooling channels, through which air was forced during cooling. Insulation was installed between the platens and the die sets to lessen the thermal inertia of the system and reduced the overall cycle time. The part was processed with the moulding cycle at a processing temperature and pressure of 400 °C and 70 bar, respectively.

Figure 2: a) Instrumented fixture used for the moulding of ROS parts, b) ROS T-shape part.

3.2 Recycled panel manufacturing

Flat panels (100 mm × 100 mm) made of recycled ROS material were manufactured using two methods. First, the recycled material consisted of previously tested short-beam strength (SBS) samples that were cut from the rib of the T-shape parts (Method 1). Their dimensions were

approximately $19.0 \text{ mm} \times 3.2 \text{ mm} \times 6.4 \text{ mm}$. Flat panels were processed with respectively 0 wt%, 20 wt%, 40 wt% and 80 wt% of recycled materials in the form of SBS samples. The recycled material was mixed with the virgin strands and the mix was laid by hand in small successive batches as homogeneously as possible both in the plane-directions and in the z-direction. The size of the virgin strands was $12.7 \text{ mm} \times 3.17 \text{ mm}$. Fig. 3a shows the final placement of the material in the mould before the processing cycle in the case of 80 wt% of recycled SBS specimens.

Second, the recycled material used was panels of approximately $50 \text{ mm} \times 50 \text{ mm} \times 3.17 \text{ mm}$, cut from the flange of the T-shape part (Method 2). The panel was made from the recycled panels stacked in the middle of the mould, as shown in Fig. 3b.

Figure 3: a) Mould cavity filled with 80 wt% SBS recycled and 20 wt% of virgin strands (Method 1), b) material placement for the processing of a panel made of recycled panels (Method 2).

The cycle used to process the recycled panels was a variation of the conventional cycle (Fig. 4). Due to the fact that the material was completely/partially consolidated, the initial applied pressure was set at only 2 bar. At this initial pressure, the material was heated to the processing temperature of $400 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and partly homogenized during 40 min. An intermediate pressure of 10 bar was applied on the material during 15 min to make sure that material temperature was homogeneous everywhere in the material. A dwell pressure of 70 bar was then applied during 15 min and the material was finally cooled down to room temperature at a rate of $10 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$.

Figure 4: Processing cycle used with recycled panels.

3.3 Testing

The panels processed with recycled material were tested in four-point bending. The tests were conducted in accordance with the ASTM D6272 standard [23]. Specimens were cut to the dimensions of 106 mm × 13 mm × 3.2 mm. They were taken at least 12 mm from the edges to prevent edge effects such as fibre alignment and distortion. The width and depth of every specimen was measured at the centre of the samples. The specimens were put in the testing fixture and loaded at a rate of 1.4 mm/min until failure. For a load span of one half of the support span, the flexural strength of the specimen was calculated from the load at break. Five specimens were tested for each panel.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the four-point bending tests with panels made from recycled SBS samples materials (Method 1) is shown in Fig. 5. The panel with 20% recycled SBS samples material yielded a similar flexural strength as the panel made of virgin material. The panel manufactured with 40% recycled material underwent a drop of 30% in flexural strength compared to the two first panels. The flexural strength continued to decrease but with lower slope for panels with higher percentage of recycled material. The trend suggests that it is possible to add up about 20% of SBS samples material without affecting the performance of the virgin material. The standard deviation in all cases was relatively similar and was not higher for lower recycling fraction (20% and 40%) than for the virgin specimen. It suggests that the distribution of SBS samples recycled material was quite homogenous in the manufactured panel.

Figure 5: Normalized flexural strength as a function of the weight fraction of recycled material (Method 1).

Fig. 6 shows the flexural strength of the panel made with recycled panels (Method 2). Interestingly, the flexural strength of the samples made of recycled panels was 25% higher than the baseline panel made of virgin strands of the same size. The difference in material placement between the two cases could explain the results. When processing a panel from virgin strands, the latter are distributed over the whole surface of the mould (100% mould coverage). When pressure is applied, the strands only flow small distances from their original position. Thus, the out-of-plane orientation imposed by the initial hand positioning of the strands was not entirely corrected. It resulted in panels with a certain degree of out-of-plane orientation. The recycled panels used in Method 2 were not distributed over the whole surface of the mould as they were stacked at the center of the mould cavity (25% mould coverage). Therefore, when pressure was applied, the strands had to flow in order to fill the mould cavity. The strands underwent a squeeze flow and the shear in-between the strands improved their out-of-plane alignment.

Figure 6: Normalized flexural strength and resin-rich fraction for the baseline and the recycled panel (Method 2).

This hypothesis was confirmed by observing the microstructure of the baseline (non-recycled) and recycled laminates. In effect, the amount of local resin-rich regions in the recycled panel using Method 2 was far lower than the baseline non-recycled panel. For the baseline panel, resin-rich regions encompassed 2.6 % of the laminate whereas it only accounted for a mere 0.6% for the squeeze flow panel. This is shown graphically in Fig. 6 and visual through a cross-sectional micrograph (Fig. 7). The squeeze-flow resulted in the shearing or spreading of the resin-rich regions thus greatly diminishing their amount. Considering the failure of the laminate, resin-rich regions are prone to failure as they can be responsible for crack initiation/propagation. It was also observed that the strands in the recycled panel are much thinner. This is an indication that intraply shear occurred due to the flow effect, resulting in a higher number of strands through the thickness of the panel, thus improving fibre orientation distribution in the panel.

Figure 7: Cross-sectional micrographs of the ROS flat panels. a) baseline panel, b) recycled panel using Method 2.

9 CONCLUSIONS

A study on the recycling of randomly oriented strand thermoplastic composites was performed using two approaches. First, small short-beam strength specimens cut from a moulded ROS part were mixed with various amounts of virgin strands. A significant drop in flexural strength was observed for content of recycled material greater than 30%. Second, recycled panels made from flat pieces cut from moulded parts had 25% higher flexural strength compared to the baseline panel made of virgin strands. It was found that the improved properties were caused by a change in overall microstructure in the laminate. The extended amount of flow of the pre-consolidated charges allowed for a reduction of resin-rich regions, improvement in out-of-plane strand alignment, and in-plane strand orientation distribution, which improved the mechanical performance. Nevertheless, this work identified the real potential of recycling ROS parts.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to greatly acknowledge financial support and materials provided by Consortium for Research and Innovation in Aerospace in Quebec (CRIAQ); the Natural Science and Engineering Research Council (NSERC); the Centre de Recherche sur les Systèmes Polymères et Composites à Haute Performance (CREPEC); the National Research Council Canada (NRC/CNRC); the industrial partners: Bell Helicopter Textron Canada Limited, Bombardier Inc., Pratt and Whitney

Canada Corp, Hutchinson Aerospace & Industry Ltd, Delastek Inc. and Avior Integrated Products Inc. D.L and B.L thank McGill University for financial assistance.

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